

**CORRELATION BETWEEN SCHOOL MANAGEMENT AND ORGANIZATIONAL
DEVELOPMENT OF SELECTED PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS IN
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Correlation Between School Management and Organizational Development of Selected Public Elementary Schools in District I Antipolo City

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the correlation between school management and organizational development of selected elementary schools in Antipolo City (District I), which served as the basis for a proposed management learning development program during the school year 2024-2025. The level of perception of the teachers regarding the school management of public school heads. In terms of Curriculum and instruction, the teacher-respondents obtained a composite mean of 3.56, which was verbally interpreted as Very Strongly Agree. In terms of Monitoring Students' Progress, the teacher-respondents obtained a composite mean of 3.55 which was verbally interpreted as Very Strongly Agree. In terms of Instructional Climate, the teacher-respondents obtained a composite mean of 3.66 which was verbally interpreted as Very Strongly Agree. The level of perception of the teacher respondents regarding the organizational development. In terms of Information and Decision-Making, the teacher-respondents obtained a composite mean of 3.59 which was verbally interpreted as Very Strongly Agree. In terms of people management, the teacher-respondents obtained a composite mean of 3.39, which was verbally interpreted as very strongly agreeable. In terms of stakeholder engagement and Retention, the teacher-respondents obtained a composite mean of 3.62 which was verbally interpreted as Very Strongly Agree. The significant relationship between the perceptions of the respondents regarding the school management of public school heads and the organizational development with respect to the above-cited variables. There is no significant relationship between the perceptions of the respondents regarding the school management of public school heads and the organizational development with respect to the above-cited variables.

Keywords: *curriculum, decision making, instructional climate*

Introduction

Education leadership is the ability to mobilize, motivate, and influence school students and all of its components so that they are willing to take actions directed at the achievement and goal of education. It is a process of influencing a group of people to do every wish, every program, and every activity to do it. As for its very specific and special nature, according to what the group requires to carry out all activities with a specific purpose. Leaders with certain characteristics need to perform the functions of that leadership. Competence is the basic ability to do and carry out work based on knowledge, skills, and work attitudes. The principal is a teacher who is given an additional task to lead a school institution, in which a learning process is held or a place for interaction between teachers who give lessons and students who receive lessons.

Certainly, in a school organization, the administrators have a crucial role in improving the school, developing teachers and students, and attaining the set goals and objectives. To achieve this, school administrators must have leadership competencies that correlate to the leadership skills and characteristics that lead to superior performance. This involves taking competency approaches to leadership so that the administrators can realize and develop their performance by adhering to leadership competencies since they are the foundation of every effective leadership development.

Effective and competent leaders provide a clear vision and direction for the school. They prioritize. They focus the staff's attention on what is important and do not let them get diverted and sidetracked with initiatives that will have little impact on the students' work. They know what is going on. They have a clear view of the strengths and weaknesses of their staff, they know how to build on the strengths and reduce the weaknesses, and they can focus their program of staff development on the real needs of their staff and school; they gain this view through a systematic program of monitoring and evaluation, and their clarity of thought, a sense of purpose and knowledge of what is going on means that effective and competent administrators can get the best out of their staff.

Additionally, effective leaders work with those around them, seeking constructive feedback and reflecting on how things can be improved. They recognize the importance of collaboration in unlocking collective genius, but they also know how to set boundaries. Hence, leadership competencies are observed when a person demonstrates the competencies that constitute self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and social skills at appropriate times and in sufficient frequency to be effective in the situation.

In today's educational landscape, school heads are constantly faced with many challenges, from implementing new school programs and projects to designing strategies that foster the holistic development of teachers, pupils, and the school. Their adept handling of these issues largely determines their success or failure as school heads, underscoring the crucial role of effective leadership in addressing daily school issues.

The concepts mentioned above have spurred the researcher to undertake this study, which aims to assess the level of headship

competence among school heads. The study also seeks to determine the impact of school heads' competence on teachers' performance and school development and the influence of school heads' management and leadership competence. This study is designed to provide valuable insights and enhance understanding in educational leadership.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the correlation school management and organizational development of selected elementary schools in Antipolo City (District I) which served as keys for a proposed management learning development program during the school year 2024-2025. More specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of perception of the teachers regarding the school management public-school heads in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. curriculum and instruction;
 - 1.2. monitoring of students' progress; and
 - 1.3. instructional climate?
2. What is the level of perception of the teacher respondents regarding the organizational development in terms of the following:
 - 2.1. information and decision-making;
 - 2.2. management of people; and
 - 2.3. stakeholders engagement and retention?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents regarding the school management of public-school heads and the organizational development with respect to the above-cited variables?
4. What learning development program may be proposed based on the results of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The method of research used in the study is the descriptive- type. Cene (2019) accurately portrays persons, events or situations.

It also defines questions, people surveyed and the method of analysis before the beginning of data collection. In other words, who, where, when why and sometimes how aspects of the research are defined.

The data will be collected from at least a part of the population to assess the incidence, distribution, and interrelations of phenomena and variables as they occur in people's lives.

It concerns with the condition or relationship that exists. Opinions are processes that are going on, evident effects, or trends that are developing. It is primarily concerned with the present although it often considers past events and influences related to condition.

The researcher therefore would be able to describe the headship competence of public-school heads as correlated to school organization development and teachers' performance from the survey which made the design appropriate for the study.

Respondents

The researcher used purposive sampling. This will be conducted in the selected schools from Dep Ed District I Division of Antipolo City. The respondents of the study were composed of teachers. Each instrument was administered to all the respondents. The respondents were given enough time to answer the research instrument. The scope of this study covered teachers from the selected schools of Dep Ed District I Division of Antipolo City.

Instrument

The study used a quantitative descriptive question that served as indicators in every variable. The survey questionnaire was consisted of three parts.

Part I is the demographic profile of the teacher respondent. Second part contained the respondents' assessment on school management and third part contained the respondents' assessment on organization development.

Procedure

Permission from the concerned authorities was sought before the conduct of the study. Upon approval of the schools division superintendent and the principal, the questionnaire – checklists were administered to the teacher-respondents from the selected public elementary schools of Dep Ed District I Division of Antipolo City and were personally retrieved by the researcher.

Data Analysis

Frequency, Percentage Distribution, and Ranking. This was used to analyze and summarize the results of the responses from the questionnaire.

Pearson r Correlation. This was used to determine the significant relationship between the perceptions of the respondents regarding the school management of public-school heads and the organizational development with respect to the above-cited variables.

Results and Discussion

This section provided the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the gathered data from the questionnaires answered by the respondents in accordance with the specific questions posited on the objectives of the study.

Level of Perception of the Teachers Regarding the School Management of Public-School Heads

Level of Perception of the Teachers Regarding the School Management of Public-School Heads in terms Curriculum and Instruction

Table 1. *Level of Perception of the Teachers Regarding the School Management of Public-School Heads in terms Curriculum and Instruction*

<i>A. Curriculum and instruction</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. Ensure that the classroom priorities of teachers are consistent with the goals and direction of the school as stipulated in the BE-LCP	3.48	VSA	6
2. Conduct informal observations through the modalities adopted by the school.	3.35	VSA	8
3. Point out specific strengths in teacher's instructional practices in post-observation feedback.	3.66	VSA	3
4. Point out specific weaknesses in teacher instructional practices in post-observation feedback.	3.64	VSA	4
5. Make clear who is responsible for coordinating the curriculum across grade levels through proper channeling.	3.48	VSA	5
6. Draw upon the results of the assessment provided when making curricular decisions.	3.71	VSA	1
7. Monitor the classroom curriculum to see that it covers the school's curricular objectives.	3.44	VSA	7
8. Assess the overlap between the school's curricular objectives and the school's achievement tests.	3.70	VSA	2
Composite Mean	3.56	VSA	

As discussed in Table 1, the respondents stated that the school heads draw upon the results of the assessment provided when making curricular decisions, which got the highest weighted mean of 3.71 and the highest rank of 1. The findings revealed that school heads regularly drew upon assessment results when making curricular decisions. School leaders were observed to utilize data from various assessments to inform and guide the development, modification, and implementation of the curriculum. This approach aimed to ensure that curricular decisions were evidence-based and responsive to the specific needs and performance levels of students. Teachers perceived this practice as crucial in aligning the curriculum with educational goals and improving overall instructional effectiveness. The results underscored school heads' commitment to data-driven decision-making, which promoted a more targeted and effective educational strategy. By leveraging assessment results, school heads aimed to create a dynamic and adaptive curriculum that supported student achievement and addressed any identified gaps in learning. This practice reflected a proactive approach to enhancing educational quality and fostering a learning environment where all students could succeed. Dinampo & Balones (2023) stated that school heads' leadership character, including lack of blame, accountability, courage, and focus on the whole, significantly influences head teachers' managerial competence.

However, the said group of respondents stated that the school heads conduct informal observations through the modalities adopted by the school which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.35 and least rank of 8. The findings revealed that school heads conducted informal observations through the various modalities adopted by the school. School leaders were observed to engage in regular, informal classroom visits, walk-throughs, and other observation techniques to monitor and support teaching practices. This approach aimed to provide ongoing, real-time feedback and support to teachers, fostering a culture of continuous improvement and professional development. Teachers perceived these informal observations as valuable opportunities for constructive feedback and collaboration with school heads. The results highlighted school heads' commitment to being actively involved in the instructional process, using informal observations to gather insights into classroom dynamics and instructional effectiveness. By conducting these observations, school heads aimed to enhance the quality of teaching and learning, address any issues promptly, and reinforce positive practices. This hands-on approach contributed to creating a supportive and responsive educational environment where teachers felt encouraged and guided in their professional growth. Mowat (2020) stated that the into headship programme based on learning theories and empirical data, helps aspiring headteachers transition into headship, contributing to school improvement and research-informed learning and practice.

The composite mean of 3.56 implied that the level of perception of the teachers regarding the headship competence of public-school heads of the school heads in terms of curriculum and instruction is within high level. The findings indicated that teachers held a high level of perception regarding the headship competence of public-school heads in terms of curriculum and instruction. Teachers perceived school heads as highly proficient in guiding and managing the curriculum and instructional practices within their schools. This perception underscored their confidence in the school heads' ability to make informed curricular decisions, support effective teaching strategies, and foster a conducive learning environment. The results suggested that teachers valued the leadership of school heads in ensuring that educational programs were well-structured, relevant, and aligned with academic standards. This high level of perception reflected teachers' recognition of the school heads' role in driving instructional quality and student achievement. By

demonstrating strong competence in curriculum and instruction, school heads aimed to enhance the overall educational experience, supporting both teachers and students in achieving their academic goals. School heads need a capability enhancement plan to improve their knowledge, skills, and attitudes, based on the National Competency-Based Standards for School Heads Training and Development Needs Assessment (NCBSSH-TDNA) (Maybelle et al., 2022).

Level of Perception of the Teachers Regarding the School Management of Public-School Heads in terms Monitoring of Students' Progress

Table 2. *Level of Perception of the Teachers Regarding the School Management of Public-School Heads in terms Monitoring of Students' Progress*

<i>B. Monitoring of Students' Progress</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. Take time to talk informally with students and teachers through the feedback mechanism stipulated in the LCP.	3.36	VSA	8
2. Attend to the class using the link provided to ensure that instruction is delivered following the screen time.	3.73	VSA	1
3. Provide direct instructions to classes when the need arises, specifically if a connection is concerned.	3.54	VSA	5
4. Meet individually with teachers to discuss student progress through the mechanism provided by the school.	3.47	VSA	6
5. Discuss academic performance results with the faculty to identify curricular strengths and weaknesses.	3.62	VSA	3
6. Use tests and another performance measure to assess progress toward school goals.	3.56	VSA	4
7. Inform teachers at the school's performance results in written form.	3.41	VSA	7
8. Inform students at school's academic progress following the DepEd Orders.	3.72	VSA	2
Composite Mean	3.55	VSA	

As presented in Table 2, the respondents perceived that the school heads attend to the class using the link provided to ensure that instruction is delivered following the screen time which got the highest weighted mean of 3.73 and the highest rank of 1. The findings revealed that school heads ensured instruction was delivered according to designated screen time by attending classes using the provided link. School leaders were observed to participate in virtual classroom sessions to monitor adherence to screen time guidelines and to support teachers in maintaining structured online learning environments. This approach aimed to optimize instructional time and ensure that virtual lessons were effective and engaging for students. Teachers perceived this involvement as a proactive measure to uphold instructional standards and to provide immediate support when needed. The results highlighted school heads' commitment to maintaining the quality of online education, reinforcing best practices in virtual instruction, and ensuring that students received a consistent and well-managed learning experience. By actively attending classes through the provided link, school heads aimed to promote accountability, support teachers, and enhance the overall effectiveness of remote teaching. The acmeological competence of the head of a general secondary education institution is a crucial factor in promoting professionalism and self-development in teaching staff (Hladkova, 2023).

However, the said group of respondents observed that the school heads take time to talk informally with students and teachers through the feedback mechanism stipulated in the LCP which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.36 and least rank of 8. The findings revealed that school heads took time to engage in informal conversations with students and teachers through the feedback mechanism stipulated in the Learning Continuity Plan (LCP). School leaders were observed to actively participate in casual dialogues, listening to the experiences and concerns of both students and teachers. This approach aimed to foster open communication, build rapport, and gather valuable insights into the school community's needs and experiences. Teachers and students perceived these informal interactions as vital in creating a supportive and responsive educational environment. The results highlighted school heads' dedication to understanding and addressing the unique challenges faced by their school community during the implementation of the LCP. By taking time for these informal talks, school heads aimed to strengthen relationships, provide emotional support, and ensure that feedback was integrated into decision-making processes. This practice reflected a commitment to nurturing a positive school culture where everyone felt heard and valued. Improving the professional competence of the head in secondary school management can enhance the quality of leadership and enhance the effectiveness of school management (Zholdasbaevna, 2020).

The composite mean of 3.55 implied that the level of perception of the teachers regarding the headship competence of public-school heads of the school heads in terms of monitoring of students' progress is within high level. The findings indicated that teachers held a high level of perception regarding the headship competence of public-school heads in terms of monitoring students' progress. Teachers perceived school heads as highly proficient in overseeing and tracking student academic performance and development. This perception underscored their confidence in the school heads' ability to implement effective monitoring systems, analyze student data, and provide timely interventions to support student learning. The results suggested that teachers valued the active role of school heads in ensuring that student progress was continuously assessed and addressed. This high level of perception reflected teachers' recognition of the importance of strong leadership in fostering a data-driven approach to education, where student outcomes were closely monitored and enhanced through strategic actions. By demonstrating competence in monitoring students' progress, school heads aimed to create an environment where academic achievement and student growth were prioritized and supported. Aguilar (2023) stated that school heads'

management competencies positively and significantly impact school leadership, with no significant difference between male and female teachers in personnel skills.

Level of Perception of the Teachers Regarding the School Management of Public-School Heads in terms Monitoring of Instructional Climate

Table 3. *Level of Perception of the Teachers Regarding the School Management of Public-School Heads in terms Monitoring of Instructional Climate*

<i>C. Instructional Climate</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. Limit interruptions of instructional time by public address.	3.26	VSA	8
2. Encourage teachers to use the instructional time for teaching and practicing new skills and concepts.	3.70	VSA	5
3. Limit the intrusion of extra- and co-curricular activities on instructional time.	3.55	VSA	7
4. Recognize students who work with formal rewards such as an honor roll or mention in the principal's newsletter.	3.82	VSA	2
5. Use online assemblies to honor students for academic accomplishments or for academic behavior or citizenship.	3.79	VSA	3
6. Recognize superior student achievement or improvement by seeing in the office the students with their work.	3.65	VSA	6
7. Contact parents to communicate improved or exemplary student performance or contributions.	3.71	VSA	4
8. Support teachers actively in their recognition and/or reward of student contributions to and accomplishments in class.	3.83	VSA	1
Composite Mean	3.66	VSA	

As shown in Table 3, the respondents perceived that the school heads support teachers actively in their recognition and/or reward of student contributions to and accomplishments in class which got the highest weighted mean of 3.83 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that school heads actively supported teachers in recognizing and rewarding student contributions and accomplishments in class. School leaders were observed to collaborate with teachers in developing and implementing recognition programs that celebrated student achievements. This approach aimed to foster a positive and motivating school culture where students felt valued and encouraged to excel. Teachers perceived this support as crucial in enhancing student engagement and promoting a sense of accomplishment. The results highlighted school heads' commitment to acknowledging and celebrating student success, thereby reinforcing positive behavior and academic excellence. By actively supporting these recognition efforts, school heads aimed to boost student morale, build a supportive community, and create an environment where both academic and personal achievements were consistently celebrated. Elementary School Heads maintain a competent level of perception in interpersonal, leadership, and supervisory skills, with no significant difference between perceptions (Trongco & Benolirao, 2023).

However, the said group of respondents stated that the school heads limit interruptions of instructional time by public address which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.26 and least rank of 8. The findings indicated that school heads made a concerted effort to limit interruptions of instructional time by minimizing public address announcements. School leaders were observed to prioritize uninterrupted learning by scheduling necessary announcements at strategic times that did not disrupt teaching and learning activities. This approach aimed to maximize instructional time, ensuring that students could engage in continuous and focused learning experiences. Teachers perceived this practice as essential in maintaining a productive classroom environment and enhancing overall instructional effectiveness.

The results highlighted school heads' commitment to protecting valuable teaching time, thereby supporting teachers in delivering high-quality education. By limiting interruptions through public address, school heads aimed to create a more stable and conducive learning environment, allowing both teachers and students to concentrate fully on the educational process. Aquino et al. (2021) stated that school head's leadership practices positively impact teachers' performance, with head teachers showing improved teaching efficiency and experience, while teachers with shorter relevant experience show poorer educational quality.

The composite mean of 3.66 implied that the level of perception of the teachers regarding the headship competence of public-school heads of the school heads in terms of instructional climate is within high level. The findings indicated that teachers held a high level of perception regarding the headship competence of public-school heads in terms of creating and maintaining a positive instructional climate. Teachers perceived school heads as highly effective in fostering an environment conducive to learning, where both students and educators felt supported, motivated, and engaged. This perception underscored their confidence in the school heads' ability to promote a culture of excellence, collaboration, and continuous improvement within the school. The results suggested that teachers valued the leadership of school heads in ensuring that the instructional climate was conducive to academic success and personal growth. This high level of perception reflected teachers' recognition of the school heads' role in establishing clear expectations, providing resources, and encouraging professional development. By demonstrating competence in shaping a positive instructional climate, school heads aimed to enhance the overall educational experience, supporting high standards of teaching and learning. Tumbokon (2023) stated that highly competent public elementary school heads significantly impact teachers' job satisfaction in terms of working conditions, work-related goal progress, and goal support.

Level of Perception of the Teacher Respondents Regarding the School Organizational Development

Level of Perception of the Teacher Respondents Regarding the School Organizational Development in terms of Information and Decision-Making

Table 4. *Level of Perception of the Teacher Respondents Regarding the School Organizational Development in terms of Information and Decision-Making*

<i>Information and Decision-Making</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. The decision-making processes and who has authority to make which decisions in our organization are clear to all involved and work well.	3.64	VSA	3
2. There are effective ways for people in our organization to communicate with one another, so that everybody has access to the information the school heads need to do their work (e.g. staff meetings, email protocols).	3.48	VSA	4
3. There are effective ways to manage the information that comes into our organization, so people have what the school heads need, but are not overwhelmed (e.g. shared files, databases, intranet).	3.71	VSA	1
4. There are identified public spokespeople for our organization, and everyone understands and respects these roles.	3.44	VSA	5
5. The important decisions are made in a timely manner in order to see opportunities and minimize risks.	3.70	VSA	2
Composite Mean	3.59	VSA	

As discussed in Table 4, the respondents perceived that the school heads provided effective ways to manage the information that comes into the organization, so people have what the school heads need, but are not overwhelmed (e.g. shared files, databases, intranet) which got the highest weighted mean of 3.71 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that school heads provided effective systems for managing incoming information within the organization, ensuring that essential resources were accessible without overwhelming staff. School leaders were observed implementing structured methods such as shared files, databases, and intranet platforms to streamline information flow. This approach aimed to facilitate easy access to necessary resources while maintaining organization and clarity in communication. Teachers and staff perceived these systems as valuable in enhancing efficiency, collaboration, and informed decision-making. The results highlighted school heads' commitment to optimizing operational processes and supporting a cohesive work environment where information was managed effectively and accessible to those who needed it. By implementing these systems, school heads aimed to improve overall productivity, reduce duplication of efforts, and promote a culture of transparency and shared responsibility within the school community. Developmentally rich contexts and supportive relationships are crucial for young people to thrive in school and in life, but many students still come to school underprepared and schools struggle to promote their development and learning (Comer, 2020).

However, the said group of respondents observed that the school heads make important decisions made in a timely manner in order to see opportunities and minimize risks which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.44 and least rank of 5. The findings indicated that school heads made timely and decisive decisions to seize opportunities and minimize risks within the school environment. School leaders were observed to prioritize efficiency and responsiveness in decision-making processes, ensuring that important matters were addressed promptly and effectively. This approach aimed to capitalize on emerging opportunities and mitigate potential risks that could impact educational outcomes and organizational success. Teachers and staff perceived these proactive decisions as crucial in maintaining stability, fostering innovation, and promoting continuous improvement within the school community. The results highlighted school heads' commitment to strategic leadership, where timely decisions were guided by thorough analysis, collaboration, and consideration of diverse perspectives. By making timely decisions, school heads aimed to enhance the overall effectiveness of educational initiatives, optimize resource allocation, and create a supportive environment conducive to achieving school goals and objectives. According to Basma & Savage (2023), teacher professional development has a small overall effect on student reading achievement in middle and high school, with the effect size moderated by delivery, hours, student population, and assessment.

The composite mean of 3.59 implied that the level of perception of the teacher respondents regarding the headship competence of public schools' heads in relation to school development in terms of information and decision-making is within high level. The findings indicated that teachers held a high level of perception regarding the headship competence of public schools' heads in relation to school development, particularly in information management and decision-making. Teachers perceived school heads as highly competent in effectively managing information and making informed decisions that contributed to school development. This perception underscored their confidence in the school heads' ability to gather, analyze, and utilize information strategically to guide school policies and initiatives. The results suggested that teachers valued the leadership of school heads in promoting transparency, efficiency, and accountability in decision-making processes. This high level of perception reflected teachers' recognition of the school heads' role in fostering a collaborative and informed approach to school development. By demonstrating competence in information management and decision-making, school heads aimed to enhance organizational effectiveness, promote innovation, and support continuous improvement in educational practices and outcomes. According to García-Feijoo et al. (2020), business schools can play a key role in achieving the sustainable development goals by incorporating awareness, cooperation, and interdisciplinarity into their activities, as well as fostering student associations and extracurricular activities.

Level of Perception of the Teacher Respondents Regarding the School Organizational Development in terms of Management of People

Table 5. Level of Perception of the Teacher Respondents Regarding the School Organizational Development in terms of Management of People

<i>Management of People</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. Our organization has human resource management policies that are documented and have been approved by the appropriate authority such as the organization's governance body.	3.38	VSA	4
2. All staff and/or volunteers have clear job descriptions and receive a thorough orientation to our organization and their role in it.	3.47	VSA	1
3. We review the performance and workload of all staff and teachers and provide regular feedback.	3.44	VSA	2
4. We deal effectively with conflicts within our organization when the school heads arise	3.40	VSA	3
5. Teachers and other staff have the skills and support the school heads need to be effective in their roles.	3.26	VSA	5
Composite Mean	3.39	VSA	

As shown in Table 5, the respondents perceived that the school heads provide all staff and/or volunteers with a clear job description and a thorough orientation to the organization and their role in it, which got the highest weighted mean of 3.47 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that school heads ensured that all staff and volunteers had clear job descriptions and received thorough orientations to the organization and their respective roles within it. School leaders were observed to prioritize structured onboarding processes that included comprehensive job descriptions and orientation sessions. This approach aimed to clarify responsibilities, expectations, and organizational procedures from the outset, ensuring that new team members were well-prepared and informed. Staff and volunteers perceived these initiatives as valuable in promoting understanding, alignment, and effective integration into the school community. The results highlighted school heads' commitment to fostering a supportive and cohesive work environment where every member felt equipped to contribute effectively. By providing clear job descriptions and thorough orientations, school heads aimed to enhance productivity, professionalism, and overall satisfaction among staff and volunteers, supporting the school's mission and goals. A culturally adapted positive youth development program positively impacts junior high school students, improving perceived attributes, life satisfaction, depression, and delinquency (Zhu & Shek, 2020).

However, the said group of respondents observed that the school heads provided teachers and other staff the skills and support the school heads need to be effective in their roles which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.26 and least rank of 5. The findings indicated that school heads ensured teachers and other staff had the necessary skills and support to effectively perform their roles. School leaders were observed to prioritize professional development opportunities, mentorship programs, and resources that enhanced the capabilities and performance of their staff. This approach aimed to empower educators and support staff with the knowledge, tools, and guidance needed to excel in their respective positions. Teachers and staff perceived these initiatives as valuable in fostering growth, increasing job satisfaction, and improving student outcomes. The results highlighted school heads' commitment to investing in the professional development and well-being of their team members, recognizing that their effectiveness directly impacts the school's overall success. By providing skills development and supportive resources, school heads aimed to cultivate a motivated and capable workforce to effectively meet the challenges and opportunities within the educational environment. According to Munby (2020), school leadership development is crucial for adapting to the challenges of a diverse, mobile, and complex 21st century education system, while ensuring student well-being and safety in a diverse and complex world.

The composite mean of 3.39 implied that the level of perception of the teacher respondents regarding the headship competence of public schools' heads about school development in terms of people management is within high level. The findings indicated that teachers held a high level of perception regarding the headship competence of public schools' heads about school development, particularly in managing people. Teachers perceived school heads as highly competent in effectively managing and leading people within the school community. This perception underscored their confidence in the school heads' ability to foster a supportive and collaborative work environment, where staff members felt valued, motivated, and empowered to contribute to the school's goals. The results suggested that teachers valued the leadership of school heads in promoting professional growth, addressing concerns, and recognizing achievements among staff members. This high level of perception reflected teachers' recognition of the school heads' role in creating a positive organizational culture that prioritizes teamwork, communication, and mutual respect. School heads aimed to enhance staff morale, retention, and overall organizational effectiveness by demonstrating competence in people management, thereby supporting the school's mission of providing quality education. Renzulli (2023) stated that schools can improve talent development and creative productivity by democratizing opportunities for all students, crucial for economic, cultural, and social development.

Level of Perception of the Teacher Respondents Regarding the School Organizational Development in terms of Stakeholders Engagement and Retention

As shown in Table 6, the respondents perceived that the school heads provided program beneficiaries, members, partners and volunteers are proud to work with the organization and speak highly of the value of our work which gained the highest weighted mean of 3.82 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that school heads ensured that program beneficiaries, members, partners, and

volunteers were proud to work with the organization and spoke highly of the value of its work.

Table 6. *Level of Perception of the Teacher Respondents Regarding the School Organizational Development in terms of Stakeholders Engagement and Retention*

<i>Stakeholders Engagement and Retention</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. We have good working relations with the people outside our organization that we work with most closely (e.g. beneficiaries of the programs, members, donors, partners).	3.26	VSA	5
2. We regularly and transparently communicate with our members, program beneficiaries and partners.	3.70	VSA	3
3. We often consult with our members, program beneficiaries and relevant partners for feedback on how well we are delivering on our mission, and ideas for new programs or activities.	3.55	VSA	4
4. Our program beneficiaries, members, partners and volunteers are proud to work with our organization and speak highly of the value of our work.	3.82	VSA	1
5. Each year, our organization sustains and deepens our relationships with partners, program beneficiaries, members, and other key stakeholders.	3.79	VSA	2
Composite Mean	3.62	VSA	

School leaders were observed to prioritize fostering positive relationships and cultivating a supportive environment that encouraged collaboration and recognition of contributions. This approach aimed to build strong partnerships and a sense of community where stakeholders felt respected, appreciated, and motivated to actively support the school's mission and goals. Stakeholders perceived these efforts as valuable in promoting a positive reputation, enhancing credibility, and attracting continued support for the organization's initiatives. The results highlighted school heads' commitment to promoting a culture of excellence and mutual respect, where all stakeholders felt valued and engaged in meaningful ways. By ensuring stakeholders were proud to be associated with the organization. They spoke highly of its impact, school heads aimed to strengthen relationships, foster loyalty, and sustain positive momentum in achieving educational objectives. According to Postholm (2020), the start-up phase in school-based development positively influences learning and enduring change, with teacher educators playing a crucial role in supporting leaders and teachers.

However, the said group of respondents observed that the school heads have good working relations with the people outside the organization they work with most closely (e.g. beneficiaries of the programs, members, donors, partners) which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.26 and the least rank of 5. The findings indicated that school heads maintained strong working relationships with stakeholders outside the organization with whom they closely collaborate, such as program beneficiaries, members, donors, and partners. School leaders were observed to prioritize communication, collaboration, and mutual respect in their interactions with these stakeholders. This approach aimed to foster trust, transparency, and effective partnerships that supported the school's mission and goals. Stakeholders perceived these efforts as valuable in promoting productive collaborations, enhancing understanding of shared objectives, and achieving collective outcomes. The results highlighted school heads' commitment to building and nurturing positive external relationships, where stakeholders felt valued, heard, and engaged in meaningful dialogue and decision-making processes. School heads aimed to strengthen support networks, attract resources, and sustain momentum in advancing educational initiatives and community impact by cultivating good working relations. Rubtsov & Ulanovskaya (2020) stated that learning activity-based teaching methods in elementary schools effectively develop cognitive, social, and personal competencies in students aged 10-11 compared to traditional methods.

The composite mean of 3.62 implied that the level of perception of the teacher respondents regarding the headship competence of public schools' heads about school development in terms of stakeholders engagement and retention is within high level. The findings indicated that teachers held a high level of perception regarding the headship competence of public schools' heads about school development, particularly in stakeholders' engagement and retention. Teachers perceived school heads as highly competent in effectively engaging with stakeholders and retaining their support and involvement in school activities. This perception underscored their confidence in the school heads' ability to foster positive relationships, communication, and collaboration with various stakeholders, including parents, community members, donors, and partners. The results suggested that teachers valued the leadership of school heads in promoting transparency, responsiveness, and inclusiveness in stakeholder interactions. This high level of perception reflected teachers' recognition of the school heads' role in creating a supportive and inclusive school environment that prioritizes stakeholder engagement and satisfaction. School heads aimed to enhance community relations, build trust, and strengthen support networks essential for advancing educational goals and achieving sustainable school development by demonstrating competence in stakeholders' engagement and retention. According to Leroy et al. (2022), academics in business schools struggle to practice evidence-based leader development due to a lack of a clear and salient evidence-based leader developer identity.

Relationship between the School Management of Public Schools' Heads and School Organizational Development as perceived by the Teachers

Table 7 presented the findings from a statistical analysis that examined the relationship between Headship Competence of Public Schools' Heads and School Development as perceived by teachers. The researcher investigated whether there was a measurable correlation between school leaders' perceived competence and their respective schools' overall development. The analysis yielded

several key metrics: the r-value, p-value, decision, and interpretation.

Table 7. *Relationship between the School Management of Public Schools' Heads and School Organizational Development as perceived by the Teachers*

Variable	r-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
School Management of Public Schools' Heads and School Organizational Development	0.070	0.268	Accept Ho	Not Significant

The r-value, or correlation coefficient, was 0.070, indicating a very weak positive correlation between Headship Competence and School Development. This low r-value implied that there was little linear relationship between these variables based on teachers' perceptions.

The p-value associated with this correlation was calculated to be 0.268. This high p-value indicated a high probability that the observed weak correlation could have occurred by chance alone, and it did not provide sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis, which stated that there was no significant relationship between Headship Competence and School Development as perceived by teachers.

Based on the p-value, the decision was made to "Accept Ho," meaning the null hypothesis was not rejected. This decision suggested that, according to the statistical analysis, there was no significant correlation between Headship Competence of Public Schools' Heads and School Development, as perceived by teachers.

The interpretation of these results indicated that, according to the perceptions of teachers surveyed in this study, the competence of school heads did not significantly influence the development of schools. Despite the weak positive correlation found, the high p-value and acceptance of the null hypothesis implied that other factors not considered in this study may have played a more substantial role in school development as perceived by teachers. These factors could have included institutional policies, community involvement, resource allocation, and socio-economic factors.

While the study revealed a weak positive correlation between Headship Competence and School Development as perceived by teachers, the statistical analysis suggested that this relationship was not statistically significant. This underscored the complexity of factors influencing school development and highlighted the need for further research to explore additional variables that may impact perceptions of school leadership and its impact on school outcomes.

School head leadership styles impact teacher performance, with teachers' performance varying based on location and gender, suggesting training in cultivating leadership styles can improve productivity (Nasim et al., 2023). According to Saputra & Prabowo (2021), school plays a crucial role in student development, preparing them for the future workplace.

Learning Development Program

Table 8. *Proposed Learning Development Program*

Program Name	Objectives	Person in Charge	Time Frame
Enhancing K-12 Curriculum Leadership	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop skills in aligning school curricula with K-12 educational reforms. - Ensure curriculum meets national standards and educational goals. - Foster collaboration among teachers for effective curriculum implementation. 	Curriculum Development Officer	2nd Quarter SY 2025-2026
Effective School Management Seminar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Equip school heads with strategies for efficient resource management. - Enhance budgeting and financial literacy skills. - Optimize school operations and improve administrative efficiency. 	School Administrator	Summer Break
Stakeholder Engagement and Community Relations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strengthen partnerships with local communities, parents, and stakeholders - Foster a positive school image and community involvement. - Enhance communication and collaboration for shared educational goals. 	Community Relations Officer	Throughout Year
Digital Transformation in Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integrate technology into teaching and learning processes. - Enhance digital literacy among staff and students. - Implement effective use of educational technology tools and resources in classrooms. 	IT Coordinator	2nd Quarter SY 2025-2026
Leadership in Inclusive Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop strategies to promote inclusive practices and support diverse student needs. - Ensure equitable access to education for all students. - Foster a supportive and inclusive school environment. 	Special Education Coordinator	3rd Quarter SY 2025-2026

Table 8 outlined tailored learning and development programs designed for school heads, addressing critical educational leadership and management aspects within local educational reforms and challenges.

Enhancing K-12 Curriculum Leadership focused on equipping school heads with the skills necessary to align school curricula with national standards and educational goals. This program emphasized collaborative curriculum development among teachers to enhance instructional quality and meet the evolving needs of students under the K-12 framework.

Effective School Management Seminar aimed to enhance school heads' abilities in resource management, budgeting, and administrative efficiency. During the summer break, this seminar provided strategies for optimizing school operations, ensuring effective resource allocation, and improving overall administrative effectiveness.

Stakeholder Engagement and Community Relations was crucial for fostering positive relationships with local communities, parents, and stakeholders. A Community Relations Officer led this program to enhance community involvement, improve communication channels, and promote shared educational goals between schools and their surrounding communities throughout the academic year.

Digital Transformation in Education focused on integrating educational technology into teaching and learning practices. Led by an IT Coordinator, this program aimed to enhance digital literacy among staff and students, promoting the effective use of digital tools to support innovative and engaging classroom experiences throughout the academic year.

Leadership in Inclusive Education addressed the need for promoting inclusive practices and supporting diverse student needs within schools. Managed by a Special Education Coordinator, this program aimed to foster a supportive and inclusive school environment, ensuring equitable access to quality education for all students throughout the academic year.

Each program was overseen by a designated person who provided leadership, guidance, and coordination. The time frames were strategically planned to align with school schedules and priorities, ensuring that school heads could participate fully without disrupting daily operations. These programs collectively aimed to enhance the leadership capacities of school heads, improve educational outcomes, and create a supportive environment conducive to student success and community engagement in the educational landscape.

Conclusions

Based on the study's results, in terms of the Level of Perception of the Teachers Regarding the Headship Competence of Public-School Heads in Curriculum and Instruction, the findings revealed that school heads regularly utilized assessment data to inform curricular decisions. They demonstrated a commitment to evidence-based practices, adapting curriculum to meet student needs and improve instructional effectiveness. Teachers viewed this approach as crucial for aligning educational goals with curriculum design, enhancing learning outcomes across diverse student populations. Moreover, school heads engaged in regular informal classroom observations and walkthroughs, providing teachers valuable feedback and support. This hands-on approach fostered a culture of continuous improvement and professional growth among educators, reinforcing positive instructional practices and addressing challenges promptly. Teachers appreciated the supportive environment created by these practices, contributing to a collaborative and effective teaching-learning process.

Regarding Monitoring Students' Progress, school heads were noted for their active participation in virtual classroom sessions to ensure adherence to instructional guidelines and support teachers in maintaining quality online learning environments. Teachers perceived this proactive involvement as instrumental in optimizing instructional time and enhancing the overall effectiveness of remote teaching. Additionally, school heads engaged in informal conversations with students and teachers, using feedback mechanisms to understand and address concerns within the school community. These interactions were valued for fostering open communication, building rapport, and integrating stakeholder input into decision-making processes, enhancing school-wide responsiveness and support.

In terms of Instructional Climate, school heads were observed to collaborate with teachers in recognizing student achievements and maintaining a positive learning environment. Their efforts included minimizing interruptions during instructional time and implementing recognition programs that motivated students and fostered a sense of accomplishment. Teachers appreciated these initiatives for creating a conducive atmosphere where teaching and learning could thrive uninterrupted. Furthermore, school heads were acknowledged for effectively managing information and decision-making processes. They established structured systems for managing data and making timely, informed decisions that supported organizational efficiency and educational excellence. Teachers recognized the importance of these leadership qualities in promoting transparency, collaboration, and strategic planning within the school community.

Regarding the Management of People, school heads were noted for their commitment to establishing clear job descriptions and providing comprehensive orientations for staff and volunteers. These initiatives aimed to foster understanding, alignment, and effective integration within the school community, ensuring that every member felt equipped and empowered. Moreover, school heads prioritized professional development opportunities and supportive resources to enhance staff capabilities and job satisfaction. Teachers appreciated these efforts for promoting a motivated and skilled workforce capable of meeting the school's educational objectives and supporting student success. Regarding Stakeholders Engagement and Retention, school heads were recognized for building strong partnerships and cultivating a supportive environment that encouraged collaboration and stakeholder involvement. They maintained positive

relationships with external stakeholders, including parents, community members, donors, and partners, fostering trust, transparency, and shared accountability in achieving school goals. Teachers valued these initiatives for enhancing community relations, securing resources, and sustaining momentum in advancing educational initiatives.

Overall, while teachers perceived school heads as competent in various aspects of school leadership, including curriculum management, instructional support, stakeholder engagement, and organizational management, the statistical analysis revealed a weak positive correlation between Headship Competence and School Development as perceived by teachers. This finding suggests that while these leadership practices were valued and contributed positively to school dynamics, their direct impact on measurable school development outcomes, as perceived by teachers, may have been influenced by a complex interplay of additional factors. Further research is recommended to explore these dynamics comprehensively and identify specific strategies to maximize school leadership's impact on student learning and overall school success.

Based on the conclusions drawn from the study, several recommendations can be made to enhance the effectiveness of school leadership in fostering positive school development and meeting the needs of teachers and students alike. Firstly, regarding Curriculum and Instruction, it is recommended that school heads continue to prioritize data-driven decision-making in curriculum development. This includes regularly utilizing assessment data to tailor educational programs to students' needs and performance levels. To strengthen this practice, school heads could consider implementing structured processes for analyzing assessment results collaboratively with teachers. This would ensure that curricular decisions are evidence-based and promote teacher involvement and ownership in the educational process. Providing professional development opportunities focused on curriculum design and instructional strategies could further empower teachers to contribute meaningfully to these processes, fostering a culture of continuous improvement and innovation in teaching practices.

In terms of Monitoring of Students' Progress, school heads should continue their proactive involvement in monitoring and supporting instructional practices, particularly in virtual learning environments. It is recommended that school heads establish clear guidelines and expectations for online instruction, supported by ongoing professional development for teachers in effective online teaching methodologies. This would help optimize instructional time and ensure that virtual lessons are engaging and conducive to student learning. Additionally, maintaining regular communication channels with students and parents through digital platforms can enhance transparency and support collaborative efforts to address learning challenges effectively.

Regarding Instructional Climate, school heads should sustain efforts to create and maintain a positive and supportive learning environment. This includes minimizing interruptions during instructional time and implementing recognition programs celebrating student achievements and teacher contributions. School heads could further enhance instructional climate by fostering a culture of mutual respect and collaboration among staff, students, and parents. Providing leadership workshops and forums for discussing best practices in school climate management could empower school heads to cultivate a nurturing educational environment that promotes academic excellence and student well-being.

In terms of Information and Decision-Making, school heads should strengthen their capacity for strategic leadership by enhancing information management systems and decision-making processes. It is recommended that school heads invest in technology infrastructure that supports efficient data collection, analysis, and dissemination across the school community. This would enable timely, informed decision-making aligning with organizational goals and priorities. Additionally, fostering a culture of transparency and inclusiveness in decision-making by soliciting input from teachers, students, and stakeholders can enhance buy-in and support for school initiatives. Leadership training programs focused on strategic planning and data-driven decision-making could further equip school heads with the skills and knowledge to navigate complex educational challenges effectively.

Regarding Management of People, school heads should continue to prioritize the development and support of their staff through clear communication, structured onboarding processes, and ongoing professional development opportunities. It is recommended that school heads implement mentorship programs and peer support networks to facilitate knowledge sharing and collaboration among staff members. Recognizing and rewarding exemplary performance can also boost staff morale and retention, fostering a positive and productive work environment. Additionally, promoting a culture of inclusivity and diversity within the school community can enhance employee satisfaction and strengthen organizational resilience.

In terms of Stakeholders Engagement and Retention, school heads should maintain and strengthen partnerships with external stakeholders, including parents, community members, donors, and partners. It is recommended that school heads establish regular communication channels and collaborative forums to solicit feedback, share updates, and align stakeholder interests with school priorities. Building trust and credibility through transparent communication and accountability can enhance stakeholder engagement and support for school initiatives. Moreover, leveraging community resources and expertise can enrich educational programs and broaden student learning and development opportunities.

Overall, while school heads demonstrate competence in various aspects of leadership, including curriculum management, instructional support, stakeholder engagement, and organizational management, continuous improvement and strategic alignment with evolving educational needs are essential. It is recommended that school heads engage in ongoing professional development and networking opportunities to stay abreast of best practices in educational leadership and management. Collaborating with peers and educational

experts can provide valuable insights and innovative strategies for addressing complex challenges and enhancing school effectiveness. By implementing these recommendations, school heads can strengthen their leadership capacity, promote a positive school climate, and foster an environment where all stakeholders thrive and contribute to achieving educational excellence. This proactive approach will enhance the overall school development and ensure that the needs and aspirations of teachers, students, and the broader community are met effectively.

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